

Teaching and Societal Attributes During Quarantine Days: A Study of Contractual Government Aided College Teachers in Kolkata

Rajarshi Mukherjee¹, Dr Shibnath Banerjee²

¹Research Scholar, ²HOD and Research Guide, Department of Business Administration,

^{1,2}JIS University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

The spread of corona virus is a potential threat to human lives in the present scenario. Almost all people have been forced to stay separate from the society, with only access to the essential commodities.

Teachers are role model for people in the society. Although a section of teachers do not get their honorarium at par with their contribution in their organizations and society, have taken initiatives in the well being of both, which the present researchers observed from contractual Government aided College teachers in Kolkata district in West Bengal.

The present researcher conducted a study in 20 colleges in Kolkata and 5 teachers serving on Contractual basis were selected on a stratified random sampling basis, based upon their experience, gender and age.

Hence a total of 100 teachers were studied. The variables included teaching skills, contribution towards research and societal contributions.

KEYWORDS: Contractual teachers, teaching skills, quarantine period, societal contributions, stratified random sampling

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Research Methodology

100 teachers were selected on the basis of stratified random sampling. They were interviewed on the basis of questionnaire sent through Survey monkey, an online portal for discussion and interactions, in order to gather data.

Observation

1. Teachers of the Age group 27 to 39 and having 5 or more years of experience, drawing salary of Rs 19,000 to 28,792 per month were considered for the study. The income was net take home amount.
2. The teachers who used teaching aids for interaction with students.
3. The teachers who delivered food and clothes to the needy people in their area and places in and around their college were also surveyed.
4. Initiative of teachers using zoom and /or Google classroom was taken into account.
5. Slides contained with cinema clips or any advertisement tools or any prose poem or analysis of the same for teachers teaching literature and /commerce or arts and unaided subjects like computer science, microbiology and \or management science was taken into consideration.

Findings:

1. Almost 80 per cent teachers, that is 80 teachers from selected 100 teachers were paid on College norms.
2. 64 teachers had already used Zoom and Google classrooms to train and teach their students. So, the total figure comes to be 64 per cent.
3. A mean average of 70.8 teachers, that is almost 71 per cent teachers arranged for interactive learning sessions with both students and colleagues.
4. Almost 56 per cent teachers took initiative in organizing conference call for students who stayed in far flung areas of the North East India or remote villages in West Bengal. The students were quarantined for the spread of Corona Virus and had poor or limited accessibility to internet or other online tools.
5. Almost 25 of 38 computer teachers which accounted for 65.78 or 66 per cent regularly arranged for online classes using Google Classroom application software or Zoom Cloud software.

A very interesting aspect that the present researcher noted was that the permanent teachers also attended demonstration sessions arranged by the contractual teachers. This was shared by the Contractual teachers themselves. They stated that more than 60 regular teachers from all colleges, computed as a mean average

method by them, attended the sessions regularly and shared feedback in their respective forums.

6. Almost 39 teachers belonging to the stream of biotechnology and microbiology shared online tools for study of enzymes, microbes and projects for hands on training of the students.
7. It was observed that 11 teachers from a total population of 38 computer teachers hired on contractual norms, accounting for 28.9 per cent of the population developed private application software to interact with the poor and the needy during the quarantine days. Considering the microbiology and biotechnology teachers, 28 out of 39 teachers rendered services as distribution of sanitizers, hand wash, soaps for people residing in their locality. This accounts for almost 73 per cent of the target population.
8. Out of 23 teachers comprising of BBA or unaided commerce streams, 100 per cent of the teachers took

regular classes online. 19 out of 23 teachers took part in societal services in and around their locality. Almost all teachers donated blood and paid money for purchasing medicines and food packets for older people, mostly of the age group 70 to 99 who could not move out to buy the bare necessities.

Conclusion:

It is still not very clear why some college created posts remain contractual and never become permanent despite all the requisite qualifications and expertise. But it was really a promising picture portrayed with many of the contractual teachers drawing much less than their state approved and/or substantive counterparts, have taken initiative of rendering contribution towards the society, without any external drive or cue. Even, no instance of any support being rendered to them by their colleges was noted by the researcher.

